

Corticomuscular Coherence Analysis for Robotic Assisted Reaching Task

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Abstract— Abstract

This study investigated the sensitivity of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a tool for analyzing neuromuscular communication, addressing the need for more precise diagnostic methods for neurological conditions. CMC, derived from EEG and EMG signals, reflects functional connectivity between the motor cortex and target muscles. The analysis utilized the open-access NeBULA database, which includes high-density EEG and EMG data. The study focused on data from 20 healthy volunteers (9 men and 11 women) aged 20-50 years, who performed a button-reaching task under three robotic assistance conditions: "Task-Free," "Task-Low," and "Task-High". Results showed that Mu-band (8-12 Hz) CMC was significantly modulated by the task, unlike the Beta (15-30 Hz) and Gamma (30-50 Hz) bands. Mean CMC values were consistently higher in the "Task-Free" condition and decreased with the introduction of robotic assistance. Furthermore, a group analysis revealed significant differences in Mu-band CMC between males and females for specific electrode pairs, such as C3-Anterior Deltoid and Cz-Anterior Deltoid, during assisted tasks. In these cases, males exhibited significantly higher mean CMC values than females. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that Mu-band CMC is a sensitive functional biomarker for neuromotor pathways. Its modulation by task demands and its ability to differentiate neural activation profiles between sexes support its use as a robust technique for investigating neuromotor biomarkers and developing more objective, personalized diagnostic and therapeutic tools.

Keywords — Corticomuscular Coherence, biomarker, EEG, EMG, BCI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Injuries to the nervous system (NS) represent a significant public health challenge, impacting patients motor and sensory function and often resulting in persistent deficits that require prolonged rehabilitation or treatment. [1]. In this context, there is a need not only for a better understanding of neurorehabilitation techniques, but also for their improvement through greater insight into the anatomic-functional remodeling of ascending and descending pathways.

Traditional evaluation and follow-up methods, as questionnaires and clinical tests [2],[3] [4], present important limitations in terms of subjectivity and low sensitivity to detect subtle changes during neural degeneration and

regeneration. Given this scenario, the search for an objective, quantitative, and parameterizable biomarkers becomes fundamental to improving diagnosis, prognosis, and personalized therapeutic planning.

Among several data processing techniques, cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) emerges as a promising tool. Obtained by the mathematical combination of brain electrophysiological signals, recorded using electroencephalography (EEG), with muscle activity measured by electromyography (EMG), CMC reflects the functional and synchronous activity between the motor cortex and the target muscle, although it does not necessarily indicate a causal relationship between them [5]. In healthy individuals, CMC is predominantly observed in the mu (8-13 Hz), beta (15-30 Hz), and sometimes gamma (above 30 Hz) frequency bands, indicating both descending motor modulation and ascending sensory feedback during motor tasks, with the rhythm found to vary in a correlated manner with the complexity of the movement performed [6, 7].

Alterations in CMC can be considered a reflection of both distinct cortical and muscular engagement patterns[6] and plasticity in spinal pathways, cortical structure, and neuromuscular junctions [8], supporting the hypothesis that such measures can strongly characterize various pathological conditions, such as neuropathies or injuries to the central nervous system.

Moreover, CMC is gaining prominence as a neuromotor biomarker, potentially representing a key tool for bioinspired operation of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) and the development of more efficient assistive technologies, as highlighted by the studies of [5, 9]. They demonstrate, respectively, (i) the correlation between cortico-muscular activation in individuals undergoing rehabilitation with varying needs for assistive devices, and (ii) the impact of a naturalistic (antropomorphic ?) implementation of supranumerary limb over corticomotor pathway plasticity and the refinement of dexterous movements.

Therefore, the present work aims to investigate the sensitivity of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a tool for analyzing neuromuscular communication in a biomarker under discovery. Using the open-access database from [10], this article tests the hypothesis that specific motor tasks

induce unic CMC pattern in movement-related frequency bands (Mu, Beta and Gamma). Additionally, the potential of CMC as a biomarker to distinguish between different study groups was explored, seeking to demonstrate its utility as a robust technique for the discovery of new neuromuscular biomarkers.

II. METODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The present study was conducted using the NeBULA (Neuromechanical Biomarkers for Upper Limb Assessment) database, published in [10]. This dataset consists of a collection of high-density electroencephalography (hd-EEG) and surface electromyography (sEMG) signals, acquired synchronously during a standardized anterior reaching task, performed both with and without of an upper limb exoskeleton support. The dataset was designed to provide a standardized resource for neuromechanical and neurofunctional biomarkers. hdEEG data were collected using the ActiCHamp system (Brain Products) with 128 electrodes arranged according to the extended 10–20 system, with sampling rate at 1000 Hz, referenced at FCz and grounded at FPz. Active electrodes with impedance below 25 k Ω were used. Muscle activity was recorded via 11 wireless sensors from the Cometa Waveplus platform, with a sampling rate of 2000 Hz. In this study, the EEG electrodes C3, C4, and Cz were included, targeting the signals related to the primary motor cortex (M1), while for EMG signal, all electrodes provided were used. Concisely, the EMG signals were acquired from: biceps brachii (long head), anterior, medial, and posterior deltoid, triceps brachii, trapezius (superior, medial, inferior), pectoralis major, pronator teres, and brachioradialis. Electrodes placement followed the SENIAM project guidelines. The Float device was used for robotic assistance: it is an upper limb exoskeleton with five degrees of freedom, designed for functional rehabilitation of the shoulder joint, with adjustable assistance control and recording of position and joint angles. All data are compliant with the BIDS (Brain Imaging Data Structure) standard, following the FAIR principles for data reproducibility and accessibility. The database structure supports studies of functional and effective connectivity, analysis of evoked potentials, inter-trial synchronization, as well as applications in machine learning-based models. Furthermore, the complete dataset comprises information from experiments involving 40 healthy volunteers (20 men and 20 women) aged between 20 and 80 years. In the present study, however, only data from the 20 volunteers aged 20 to 50 years were analyzed, of whom 9 were men and 11 were women.

B. Task

The experimental protocol consisted of three sets of ten repetitions of a standardized anterior reaching task, during which participants were required to touch one of three targets positioned on a custom touchscreen panel in front of them. Each trial was manually initiated by the experimenter, who illuminated one of the targets in a pseudo-random order, thereby indicating which target should be reached in that trial. Once the the indicated target was touched, the trial was considered complete, and the participant should return

to resting position, with their hand placed on their knee. The selected task aligns with the motor skill taxonomy proposed by [11]. Each set of repetitions was performed under three distinct conditions: (1) without assistance (task-free), (2) with low assistance (task-high), or (3) with high assistance (task-high), provided by the robotic exoskeleton (The Float device). The order of these assistance conditions was randomized for each participant to minimize adaptation bias.

Fig. 1. This figure outlines the methodological flow of the study. The research utilized the open-access NeBULA (Neuromechanical Biomarkers for Upper Limb Assessment) database, which contains high-density EEG and surface EMG signals from 40 healthy volunteers (20 men and 20 women). This study focused on data from 20 volunteers (9 men and 11 women) aged 20 to 50 years. Participants performed a standardized anterior reaching task, touching one of three targets on a custom touchscreen. The task was performed under three robotic assistance conditions: "Task-Free" (without assistance), "Task-Low" (with low assistance), and "Task-High" (with high assistance). The aim was to investigate the sensitivity of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a neuromuscular biomarker. The CMC was calculated for specific EEG-EMG electrode pairs, focusing on the C3, C4, and Cz EEG electrodes and arm muscles, to test the hypothesis that motor control tasks induce a specific CMC pattern in the Mu and Beta frequency bands.

C. Preprocessing & Signal analysis

The EEG data provided was already preprocessed, having undergone band-pass filtering (0.5–50 Hz), averaging, and artifact removal using the Clean Rawdata plugin (EEGLAB). In addition, rejected channels were interpolated, and the cleaned data was segmented according to the task onset markers described below. The EMG signal data was preprocessed in a similar manner, with windowing matching the EEG, filtered with a 4th-order Butterworth filter (20–350 Hz), and denoised using the Daubechies 'db4' wavelet.

Given the specific requirements of our subsequent analyses, dataset was submitted to an additional preprocessing stage. For this study, the EEG channels C3, C4, and Cz were band-pass filtered between 3 and 50 Hz using 4th- and 6th-order Butterworth filters. The EEG sampling rate was maintained at 1000 Hz. The narrower low-frequency cutoff was implemented to minimize residual ocular artifacts and low-frequency noise.

EMG signals were further subjected to band-pass filtering between 10 and 450 Hz. The filtered signals were then downsampled from 2000 Hz to 1000 Hz, rectified, and normalized by the root mean square (RMS) value of the entire signal. This filtering step focused on the muscle power band, while rectification and RMS normalization are important procedures for preparing the signal for coherence

analysis.

Continuous EEG and EMG data were then segmented into trials based on event markers available within the dataset (marker file, .vmrk). Each trial was defined as the interval between a 'StartTrial' and an 'EndTrial' marker, corresponding to the onset of preparation for movement execution and the subject's return to rest, respectively. Additional markers include 'G' (Go), for the initiation of the voluntary action, and 'R', for the moment of button/target touch or reach. The 'G' marker was used to divide each trial into Baseline or Rest (from 'StartTrial' to 'G') and Task segments (from 'G' to 'EndTrial').

D. Cortico-Muscular Coherence

Functional connectivity is defined as the "statistical dependence between distant neurophysiological events." [12] In this context, we sought to explore cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) data in pursuit of a functional biomarker for neural activity and its synchrony with muscle activation. Cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) is a specific application of coherence analysis focused on examining the functional synchronization between the motor cortex and the electrical activity of peripheral muscles, typically recorded via EMG. CMC allows us to investigate how rhythmic brain oscillations are related to muscle activation, particularly during voluntary movements. The equation for CMC is the same as that for generic coherence, but applies to EEG and EMG signals as follows:

$$\text{CMC}_{\text{EEG,EMG}}(f) = \frac{|S_{\text{EEG,EMG}}(f)|^2}{S_{\text{EEG,EEG}}(f) S_{\text{EMG,EMG}}(f)}. \quad (1)$$

where $S_{\text{EEG,EMG}}(f)$ represents the cross-spectrum between EEG and EMG for some frequency (f), $S_{\text{EEG,EEG}}(f)$ the autospectrum of the EEG for the same frequency f and $S_{\text{EMG,EMG}}(f)$ the autospectrum of the EMG for the same frequency f .

For this study, cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) was calculated for each of the previously described EEG-EMG electrode pairs, in each participant, across all trials, spanning the three reach task conditions, levels of robotic assistance, and frequency bands, using the "wcoherence" function in MATLAB. The analysis focused on three specific frequency bands, well-established in the motor control literature: mu (8–12 Hz), beta (15–30 Hz), and gamma (30–50 Hz) [13, 14].

E. Statistical Analysis

The CMC results were aggregated by calculating the mean across all trials for each subject and for every combination of task, frequency band, and electrode pair. Two hypotheses were subsequently tested. First, we investigated the combination of electrode pair \times frequency band \times support level, hypothesizing that CMC would differ between electrode pairs due to the participation of each muscle group in movement precision. If this first hypothesis was not rejected, a second hypothesis was tested, proposing significant differences in CMC between males and females for those electrode pairs identified as relevant in the initial analysis. For the first hypothesis, a repeated measures

ANOVA was performed for mu, beta, and gamma bands. By which, the model included the following factors: "Task" (task-free, task-low, task-high) and "Electrode Pair" (e.g., C3–Biceps, C4–Triceps). When a significant interaction effect was detected, post-hoc multiple comparisons were conducted to identify which task–electrode pair combinations exhibited statistically significant differences. As for the second hypothesis, for each electrode pair of interest and for each of the three task conditions (task-free, task-low, task-high), their mean CMC was compared between the two sex groups (male and female). Statistical analysis of group differences was performed using a two-sample independent t-test (t-test2). A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted to determine statistically significant differences.

III. RESULTS

A. CMC was significantly increased for mu band during tasks

A repeated-measures ANOVA was conducted to test the Task \times Electrode Pair interaction across three bands—Mu, Beta, and Gamma (Figure 2). Although some pairwise differences were observable, Beta and Gamma showed uniformly low CMC (<0.1 on the 0–1 scale), indicating no task-relevant modulation [12]. In contrast, the Mu band showed a highly significant interaction effect (p -value of 1.518; $p < 0.05$), indicating that corticomuscular coupling between M1 and arm muscles varies with the task performed. The impact of task on Mu was significant, with CMC highest in the task-free condition and no difference between the assisted conditions. Post-hoc multiple comparisons localized the most robust effects to C3–Triceps, C3–Anterior Deltoid, C4–Triceps, Cz–Anterior Deltoid, and Cz–Triceps.

B. Electrodes \times Tasks

To examine whether and how cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) varied across tasks, we ran one-way ANOVAs for each of the five most relevant EEG–EMG pairs. All five showed significant task-related differences in CMC. A brief summary follows:

TABLE 1. One-way ANOVA results for electrode pairs and task conditions. Means (M) and standard deviations (SD) of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC).

Electrode Pair	p-value	CMC (Average \pm SD)
C3–Triceps	0,0008	Task-Free: 0,1329 \pm 0,0101; Task-Low: 0,1150 \pm 0,0183; Task-High: 0,1148 \pm 0,0192
C3–Ant Deltoid	0,0001	Task-Free: 0,1377 \pm 0,0074; Task-Low: 0,1223 \pm 0,0145; Task-High: 0,1205 \pm 0,0139
C4–Triceps	0,0049	Task-Free: 0,1330 \pm 0,0113; Task-Low: 0,1157 \pm 0,0194; Task-High: 0,1181 \pm 0,0200
Cz–Triceps	0,0021	Task-Free: 0,1306 \pm 0,0108; Task-Low: 0,1130 \pm 0,0180; Task-High: 0,1148 \pm 0,0194
Cz–Ant Deltoid	0,0002	Task-Free: 0,1360 \pm 0,0089; Task-Low: 0,1209 \pm 0,0139; Task-High: 0,1205 \pm 0,0139

Corticomuscular Coherence versus Frequency Band

Corticomuscular Coherence in Mu Band Frequency

Fig. 2. Cortico-Muscular Coherence (CMC) Analysis by Frequency Band This figure presents the CMC analysis for the Beta, Gamma, and Mu frequency bands across the three task conditions. A repeated measures ANOVA revealed a highly significant interaction effect in the Mu band ($p = 1.518 \times 10^{-6}$), indicating that Mu-band coherence is significantly modulated by the task and electrode pair. In contrast, the Beta and Gamma bands showed no substantial differences in connectivity patterns among electrode pairs based on the task, with p -values of 0.746 and 0.770, respectively. Post-hoc analyses for the Mu band showed that most significant CMC differences occurred between the non-assisted ("Task-Free") and assisted conditions ("Task-Low" and "Task-High"). Mean CMC values were consistently higher in the absence of assistance, particularly for the C3-Triceps, C3-Anterior Deltoid, Cz-Anterior Deltoid, and Cz-Triceps pairs. This suggests that external assistance may decrease the need for cortical-muscle synchronization.

C. Men versus Women mu bands

Finally, a comparative analysis of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) in the Mu band was conducted between males ($n = 9$) and females ($n = 11$), considering the task-free, task-low, and task-high conditions, and focusing on the most relevant electrode pairs identified previously. The results showed that, for the C3–Anterior Deltoid pair during the task-high condition, mean CMC values in males ($M = 0.1276$; $SD = 0.0076$) were significantly higher than in females ($M = 0.1147$; $SD = 0.0155$), with $p = 0.0355$. In the same region during the task-low condition, males also exhibited higher mean CMC ($M = 0.1306$; $SD = 0.0085$) compared to females ($M = 0.1155$; $SD = 0.0151$), with $p = 0.0156$. For the Cz–Anterior Deltoid pair, it was similarly observed that in the task-high condition, mean CMC in males ($M = 0.1278$; $SD = 0.0088$) was greater than in females ($M = 0.1146$; $SD = 0.0148$), with $p = 0.0294$. During the task-low condition, mean CMC remained higher in males ($M = 0.1291$; $SD = 0.0084$) relative to females ($M = 0.1143$; $SD = 0.0141$), with $p = 0.0126$. Conversely, for the task-free condition and for electrode pairs involving the Triceps muscle, no statistically significant differences between sexes were identified. In summary, these findings indicate that Mu-band CMC exhibits sex-dependent modulation, manifesting significantly for the Anterior Deltoid muscle during motor control tasks involving robotic assistance (task-low and task-high), with $p < 0.05$. In these contexts, males consistently displayed higher mean CMC values compared to females (see Figure 3), reinforcing

the potential as a biomarker.

IV. DISCUSSION

Pursuing advance toward a more comprehensive understanding of measurable and clinically relevant biomarker parameters, the primary objective of this study was to investigate the sensitivity of cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a component of a neuromuscular biomarker. Specifically, we explored its modulation during motor control tasks performed under varying levels of robotic assistance (exoskeleton) and examined its variations across sex groups. Under physiological conditions, the greatest expression of CMC is usually observed in the beta band (14–20 Hz) during static force production and fine motor control, and in the gamma band (above 30 Hz) during dynamic movements [12]. However, in the present study, a significant interaction effect between Task and Electrode Pair was found specifically for the Mu band, but not for other brain rhythms, with a highly significant p -value ($p = 1.518 \times 10^{-6}$). This result may be related to the fact that the task performed by the participants was visuomotor, dynamic, repetitive and relatively non-complex. The Mu rhythm is notably involved in preventing interference with motor programming processing during movement preparation, through its inhibition [15], and it is also potentially associated with motor learning by repetition [16]. Furthermore, increases in Mu activity appear to be related to the complexity of the motor task and the amount of cortical processing required [6].

Corticomuscular Coherence – Mu Frequency Band: Male versus Female

Fig. 3. Cortico-Muscular Coherence (CMC) in Mu Band: Male versus Female This figure compares the CMC values in the Mu band between males and females for specific electrode pairs across the three task conditions. The analysis revealed significant differences between sexes for the C3-Anterior Deltoid and Cz-Anterior Deltoid pairs during the assisted motor control tasks ("Task-Low" and "Task-High"). For the C3-Anterior Deltoid pair, mean CMC was significantly higher in males compared to females in the "Task-High" condition ($p=0.0355$) and "Task-Low" condition ($p=0.0156$). Similarly, for the Cz-Anterior Deltoid pair, males exhibited significantly higher mean CMC in the "Task-High" ($p=0.0294$) and "Task-Low" ($p=0.0126$) conditions. No statistically significant differences were found between sexes for the "Task-Free" condition or for the electrode pairs involving the Triceps muscle. These results suggest that Mu-band CMC exhibits a sex-dependent modulation, particularly for the Anterior Deltoid muscle during assisted motor control tasks.

Thus, although both Beta and Mu bands are traditionally associated with motor control [7], the greater sensitivity of the Mu band observed in our results may indicate a more robust or specific modulation in response to the characteristics of the low-complexity reaching tasks employed in this study. The post-hoc analyses for the Mu band deepened this understanding, showing that most significant differences in CMC occurred between the non-assisted (task-free) condition and the assisted conditions (task-low and task-high). Mean CMC values were consistently higher in the absence of assistance, a pattern observed across multiple electrode pairs, particularly C3–Triceps, C3–Anterior Deltoid, C4–Triceps, Cz–Anterior Deltoid, and Cz–Triceps. This finding corroborates previous studies reporting a reduction in CMC with the introduction of robotic assistance [5], as external assistance may decrease the need for cortex and muscle synchronization. The absence of significant differences between task-low and task-high in most electrode pairs suggests that the distinction between these two levels of assistance may not be sufficiently pronounced to generate additional modulations detectable by

CMC. However, the exception observed for the C4–Pronator Teres pair between task-low and task-high ($p=0.042$) may indicate a muscle-specific or laterality effect that warrants further investigation, as well as a deeper exploration of the Mu rhythm's role in skilled versus unskilled movements. Subsequent analyses comparing CMC values for each electrode pair across tasks confirmed that CMC varies as a function of task for all relevant pairs, with ANOVA p -values below 0.05. Descriptive statistics revealed that CMC in the task-free condition was consistently greater than in the task-low and task-high conditions for most pairs, which may reflect a pattern of deactivation or different modulation of CMC in states of rest or lower motor control demand. This finding aligns with [5], who observed increased corticomuscular coupling inversely proportional to the level of assistance (exoskeleton or electrical stimulation). Further aiming to validate the sensitivity of CMC as a candidate biomarker, we assessed its ability to detect tangible differences between male and female groups. It is well established that sex-related differences in motor control and neural activity remain poorly understood. However, studies such as [17, 18] highlight the existence of sex-specific differences in both muscular (electrophysiological and force) and metabolic markers, as observed during task performance and in the context of age-related neuromotor impairment, respectively. In our investigation, the analysis of CMC differences between males and females in the Mu band revealed significant results. We observed that the average CMC for males was significantly greater than for females specifically for C3–Anterior Deltoid and Cz–Anterior Deltoid electrode pairs, particularly when comparing assisted with non-assisted tasks (task-low and task-high). These findings suggest that although both groups showed the expected reduction in CMC with the addition of robotic assistance, the decrease in CMC was more pronounced in females than in males for certain electrode pairs. This could potentially be explained by differential engagement in human–machine interaction between males and females; It may also suggest that the mu activity in CMC studies differs from brain activity studies in terms of laterality, hence shoulder muscles usually presents a evident ipsilateral activation for mu band however and a potential highlight over Anterior Deltoid activity in controlled reaching tasks. However, further analyses of other frequency bands for the same electrode pairs, as well as an exploration of EEG electrodes associated with motor planning and programming, are needed for more definitive conclusions. Despite its findings, this study is subject to certain limitations that warrant discussion. The use of an open-access database, while crucial for reproducibility, introduced challenges related to data quality and collection history. Specifically, incomplete documentation regarding rejected electrodes introduced uncertainty during the preprocessing stage. Additionally, the EEG data exhibited a degree of noise which, although mitigated, may have influenced the variability of the results. Finally, the nature of the reaching task, categorized as low complexity, may have limited the CMC analysis and the applicability of the findings to more skilled or complex movements, which are particularly relevant in neuromotor rehabilitation. In summary, this study demonstrated the sensitivity of Mu-band cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a functional marker of neuromotor pathways. Our results indicate that CMC

is significantly modulated according to motor control task demands, exhibiting a desynchronization signature during movement compared to rest. Moreover, group analysis revealed significant CMC differences between males and females in specific electrode pairs and during assisted motor control tasks, suggesting that CMC holds the potential to differentiate neural activation profiles across populations. These findings support the use of CMC as a robust technique for investigating neuromotor biomarkers and pave the way for the development of more objective and personalized diagnostic and therapeutic tools.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the sensitivity of Mu-band cortico-muscular coherence (CMC) as a potential functional marker of neuromotor pathways in low-complexity visuomotor tasks. Our results indicate that CMC is significantly modulated according to the task, exhibiting a desynchronization signature during robotically assisted movement compared to free movement conditions. Furthermore, the group analysis revealed significant differences in CMC between males and females in specific electrode pairs and during assisted motor control tasks, suggesting that CMC has the potential to distinguish neural activation profiles across different populations. These findings support the use of CMC as a robust technique for the investigation of neuromotor biomarkers.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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